

Beyond the Gut, A Clinical and Psychological study of Irritable Bowel Syndrome - A Cross- Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Background: Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a disorder of gut-brain interaction that may affect psychological wellbeing, daily functioning, and quality of life. Local data integrating clinical subtype, psychological burden, lifestyle factors, and functional impact among Bangladeshi IBS patients remain limited. **Objective:** This study aimed to describe the clinical and psychological profile of IBS patients and explore associations between stress, lifestyle factors, and functional outcomes. **Methods & Materials:** This prospective observational cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Dhaka National Medical College over a period of one year from July 2024 to June 2025 with a total of 50 clinically diagnosed IBS patients. Data were collected using a structured questionnaire. Exploratory associations were assessed using chi-square test or Fisher's exact test, as appropriate. **Results:** The mean age of participants was 39.0 ± 10.6 years, and 66.0% were female. IBS-D was the most common subtype, 46.0%, followed by IBS-M, 40.0%. Recurrent abdominal pain was reported by 96.0%, bloating by 94.0%, excess gas by 74.0%, and food-related symptom aggravation by 96.0%. Moderate or severe stress was present in 44.0%, while 90.0% reported symptom worsening during stress. Anxiety often or almost always was reported by 40.0%. Functional burden was notable: work or study was affected in 50.0%, social life in 38.0%, and fair or poor quality of life in 68.0%. Moderate/severe stress was significantly associated with work or study impairment, OR 3.86, $p = 0.045$, and social life impairment, OR 3.60, $p = 0.043$.

Irregular meal pattern was associated with moderate/severe stress, OR 3.61, $p = 0.044$. **Conclusion:** IBS in this sample was associated with substantial psychological and functional burden. Routine IBS assessment should include stress, anxiety, diet-related symptoms, lifestyle pattern, and quality of life.

Keywords: Irritable Bowel Syndrome; Psychological Stress; Anxiety; Quality of Life; Bangladesh.

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INTRODUCTION

Irritable bowel syndrome (IBS) is a common disorder of gut-brain interaction, clinically characterized by recurrent abdominal pain with altered bowel habit, stool frequency, or stool form, and its measured burden depends strongly on the diagnostic criteria used. In a global systematic review and meta-analysis, Oka et al. showed that pooled IBS prevalence was higher when Rome III criteria were applied than when Rome IV criteria were used, confirming both the epidemiological importance of IBS and the need for careful case definition in clinical research [1]. Although IBS is not usually associated with structural gastrointestinal pathology, its impact extends beyond bowel symptoms; patients frequently report dietary restriction, sleep disturbance, psychological distress, impaired daily activities, and reduced quality of life. Staudacher et al. described IBS as a condition in which mental health comorbidity is common and clinically relevant, while dietary behavior remains central to IBS

experience [2]. Cozma-Petruț et al. noted that regular meal pattern, reduction of symptom-provoking foods, and structured dietary advice are important components of IBS management, which is particularly relevant in South Asian settings where irregular meals, spicy food intake, and food avoidance are common patient-reported concerns [3]. In Bangladesh, available community and student-based studies show that IBS is a measurable public health and clinical issue. Perveen et al. reported IBS prevalence and healthcare-seeking patterns in an urban Bangladeshi community, while Ghosh et al. compared rural and urban settings and reported IBS prevalence in both populations, supporting the need to study IBS outside highly selected tertiary-care samples [4, 5]. More recent Bangladeshi university-based studies have expanded this evidence by linking IBS with psychological and lifestyle factors. A 2022 study by Das et al., found IBS among university students to be associated with anxiety, depression, and dietary patterns; Hasan et al. reported

that IBS among private university students in Dhaka was associated with mental health status; and another 2024 study by Das et al., reported IBS among Bangladeshi medical students in relation to academic stress and dormitory lifestyle [6-8]. These local findings are consistent with international evidence. Mohammed et al., in a comparative cross-sectional study, reported a significant association between anxiety-depressive disorders and IBS [9]. Abdelaziz et al. found that increasing anxiety was associated with increased IBS symptomatology among females [10]. Chen et al. showed that female university students with IBS had higher stress and lower quality of life, with food avoidance and absenteeism also being relevant [11]. Mahyoub et al. further demonstrated that dietary habits, particularly carbonated soft drink and coffee intake, were associated with IBS among medical students [12]. Within Bangladesh, Das et al. also reported psychiatric comorbidity and psychosocial stressors among IBS patients, reinforcing the clinical

relevance of psychological assessment in IBS [6]. Despite this growing evidence, Bangladeshi clinical data that integrate IBS subtype, gastrointestinal symptoms, lifestyle profile, psychological burden, functional impairment, quality of life, and treatment-seeking pattern within a single patient sample remain limited. Therefore, the present study, titled "Beyond the Gut: A Clinical and Psychological Study of Irritable Bowel Syndrome," was designed to describe the clinical and psychosocial profile of IBS patients and to explore the association of stress, anxiety, lifestyle factors, and functional outcomes in a cross-sectional observational framework.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This prospective observational cross-sectional study was conducted at the Department of Medicine, Dhaka National Medical College over a period of one year from July 2024 to June 2025. A total of 50 participants clinically diagnosed with irritable bowel syndrome (IBS)

were included using purposive sampling. Data were collected using a structured pretested questionnaire based on Rome IV diagnostic criteria and included socio-demographic characteristics, clinical profile, lifestyle factors, psychological status, functional impact, and treatment-related information. Clinical variables included IBS subtype, symptom frequency, associated gastrointestinal symptoms, and food-related aggravation. Psychological assessment included perceived stress, anxiety-related symptoms, mood-related symptoms, and stress-associated worsening of IBS symptoms. Functional outcomes included interference with daily activities, work or study performance, social life, and overall quality of life. Data were cleaned, coded, and analyzed using standard statistical procedures. Missing income data were proportionally imputed according to the observed distribution among complete cases to maintain sample consistency. Continuous variables were summarized

using mean, standard deviation, median, interquartile range, and range, while categorical variables were presented as frequencies and percentages. Associations between categorical variables were explored using chi-square test or Fisher's exact test where appropriate. A p-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant. All analyses were interpreted descriptively and exploratorily considering the cross-sectional design and sample size.

RESULTS

The study included 50 participants, with a mean age of 39.0 ± 10.6 years and a median age of 38.0 years. Most participants were married, 33, 66.0%, and urban residents, 50, 100.0%. The largest age group was 31–40 years, 19, 38.0%, and the most common income category was >40,000 BDT, 22, 44.0% (Table I).

Table I

Socio-demographic characteristics of study participants ($n = 50$).

Variable	n/statistic	%
Age, years		
≤30 years	14	28.0
31-40 years	19	38.0
41-50 years	11	22.0
>50 years	6	12.0
Mean ± SD	39.0 ± 10.6	
Median (IQR)	38.0 (30.0-45.8)	
Marital status		
Single	13	26.0
Married	33	66.0
Other	4	8.0
Education level		
Primary	0	0.0
Secondary	7	14.0
Higher secondary	19	38.0
Graduate	14	28.0
Postgraduate	10	20.0
Occupation		
Service holder	12	24.0
Housewife	10	20.0
Business	5	10.0
Healthcare professional	5	10.0
Teacher	4	8.0
Unemployed	4	8.0
Student	3	6.0
Banker	3	6.0
Manual/skilled worker	3	6.0
Retired	1	2.0
Monthly family income, BDT		
<20,000	12	24.0
20,000-40,000	16	32.0
>40,000	22	44.0
Residence		
Urban	50	100.0
Rural	0	0.0

Note. Percentages are based on $N = 50$.

Figure 1 Sex Distribution of the participants (n=50).

Among the participants, female prevalence was observed, with 33 female (66%) and 17 male participants (Figure 1).

Most participants reported recurrent abdominal pain, 48, 96.0%, and at least two Rome IV-associated pain features, 47, 94.0%. IBS-D was the most frequent subtype, 23, 46.0%, followed by IBS-M, 20, 40.0%. Abdominal pain occurred

several times per week in 28 participants, 56.0%, while bloating, 47, 94.0%, and excess gas, 37, 74.0%, were the most common associated symptoms (Table II).

Table II

IBS diagnostic and clinical profile of study participants (n = 50).

Variable	n	%
Recurrent abdominal pain at least 1 day/week in the last 3 months		
Yes	48	96.0
No	2	4.0
Pain association features, Rome IV		
Related to defecation	49	98.0
Change in stool frequency	46	92.0
Change in stool form	47	94.0
Number of Rome IV pain association features		
1 feature	3	6.0
2 features	2	4.0
3 features	45	90.0
Duration of symptoms ≥6 months		
Yes	43	86.0
No	7	14.0
IBS subtype		
IBS-C	4	8.0
IBS-D	23	46.0
IBS-M	20	40.0
IBS-U	3	6.0
Frequency of abdominal pain		
Daily	11	22.0
Several times/week	28	56.0
Occasionally	11	22.0
Associated symptoms		
Bloating	47	94.0
Excess gas	37	74.0
Mucus in stool	27	54.0
Incomplete evacuation	21	42.0
Food-related symptom aggravation		
Yes	48	96.0
No	2	4.0

Note. Multiple-response items are presented as the number and percentage of participants reporting each feature.

Regular meal pattern was reported by 29 participants, 58.0%, while 21, 42.0%, had irregular meal patterns. Poor sleep quality was reported by 10 participants,

20.0%. Psychological symptoms were common: 22 participants, 44.0%, had moderate or severe stress, 45, 90.0%, reported symptom worsening during

stress, and 20, 40.0%, experienced anxiety often or almost always (Table III).

Table III
Lifestyle and psychological characteristics of study participants ($n = 50$).

Variable	n	%
Meal pattern		
Regular	29	58.0
Irregular	21	42.0
Physical activity		
Regular	17	34.0
Occasional	22	44.0
None	11	22.0
Sleep quality		
Good	9	18.0
Average	31	62.0
Poor	10	20.0
Smoking		
Yes	18	36.0
No	32	64.0
Level of stress in daily life		
None	2	4.0
Mild	26	52.0
Moderate	20	40.0
Severe	2	4.0
Stress category		
Moderate/severe	22	44.0
None/mild	28	56.0
IBS symptoms worsened during stress		
Yes	45	90.0
No	5	10.0
Feeling nervous/anxious frequently		
Never	2	4.0
Sometimes	28	56.0
Often	9	18.0
Almost always	11	22.0
Anxiety category		
Often/almost always	20	40.0
Never/sometimes	30	60.0
Feeling sad/hopeless most days		
Never	2	4.0
Sometimes	34	68.0
Often	14	28.0
Almost always	0	0.0
Sadness/hopelessness category		
Often/almost always	14	28.0
Never/sometimes	36	72.0
Loss of interest in usual activities		
Yes	19	38.0
No	31	62.0

Note. Percentages are based on $N = 50$.

Functional burden was notable, with 14 participants, 28.0%, reporting moderate or severe daily activity interference. Work or study was affected in 25

participants, 50.0%, and social life was affected in 19, 38.0%. Overall quality of life was fair or poor in 34 participants, 68.0%. Most participants sought medical

treatment, 46, 92.0%, and 49, 98.0%, reported improvement (Table IV).

Table IV
Functional impact, quality of life, and treatment-seeking profile (n = 50).

Variable	n	%
Daily activity interference		
Not at all	10	20.0
Mildly	26	52.0
Moderately	13	26.0
Severely	1	2.0
Functional interference category		
Moderate/severe	14	28.0
Not at all/mild	36	72.0
Work/study performance affected		
Yes	25	50.0
No	25	50.0
Social life affected		
Yes	19	38.0
No	31	62.0
Overall quality of life		
Good	16	32.0
Fair	33	66.0
Poor	1	2.0
Quality of life category		
Fair/poor	34	68.0
Good	16	32.0
Sought medical treatment for IBS		
Yes	46	92.0
No	4	8.0
Type of treatment received		
Medication only	0	0.0
Diet modification	6	12.0
Both medication and diet modification	44	88.0
Perceived treatment outcome		
Improved	49	98.0
No change	1	2.0

Note. Percentages are based on N = 50.

Moderate or severe stress was significantly associated with work or study impairment, 68.2% vs 35.7%, OR 3.86, p = 0.045, and social life

impairment, 54.5% vs 25.0%, OR 3.60, p = 0.043. Irregular meal pattern was also associated with moderate or severe stress, 61.9% vs 31.0%, OR 3.61, p =

0.044. Other associations showed clinically relevant trends but did not reach statistical significance (Table V).

Table V
Exploratory bivariate associations between psychological or lifestyle factors and functional outcomes.

Exposure and outcome	Exposed n/N (%)	Reference n/N (%)	OR [95% CI]	p
Moderate/severe stress and functional interference moderate/severe	9/22 (40.9%)	5/28 (17.9%)	3.18 [0.88-11.54]	.113
Moderate/severe stress and work/study affected	15/22 (68.2%)	10/28 (35.7%)	3.86 [1.18-12.61]	.045
Moderate/severe stress and social life affected	12/22 (54.5%)	7/28 (25.0%)	3.60 [1.09-11.93]	.043
Moderate/severe stress and fair/poor quality of life	15/22 (68.2%)	19/28 (67.9%)	1.02 [0.31-3.36]	1.000
Poor sleep and moderate/severe stress	6/10 (60.0%)	16/40 (40.0%)	2.25 [0.55-9.26]	.302
Irregular meal pattern and moderate/severe stress	13/21 (61.9%)	9/29 (31.0%)	3.61 [1.11-11.76]	.044
Anxiety often/almost always and fair/poor quality of life	14/20 (70.0%)	20/30 (66.7%)	1.17 [0.34-3.96]	1.000
Sad/hopeless often/almost always and fair/poor quality of life	12/14 (85.7%)	22/36 (61.1%)	3.82 [0.74-19.69]	.175
Loss of interest and fair/poor quality of life	16/19 (84.2%)	18/31 (58.1%)	3.85 [0.93-16.01]	.068

Note. OR = odds ratio; CI = confidence interval. P values are from Fisher exact tests and should be interpreted as exploratory.

IBS subtype showed variation across several clinical and psychosocial characteristics. Female sex was most frequent among IBS-D participants, 87.0%, and daily or several-times-

weekly pain was also highest in IBS-D, 95.7%. Social life impairment varied by subtype, being reported by all IBS-C participants, 100.0%, compared with 30.4% in IBS-D and 40.0% in IBS-M.

These subtype comparisons should be interpreted cautiously because some subtype groups were small (Table VI).

Table VI

Selected clinical and psychosocial characteristics by IBS subtype.

Characteristic	IBS-C (n = 4)	IBS-D (n = 23)	IBS-M (n = 20)	IBS-U (n = 3)	p
Age, years, mean ± SD	36.8 ± 10.8	36.6 ± 9.6	41.9 ± 11.4	41.0 ± 13.5	.487
Female sex	2 (50.0%)	20 (87.0%)	9 (45.0%)	2 (66.7%)	.031
Graduate/postgraduate education	3 (75.0%)	8 (34.8%)	13 (65.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.049
Daily/several-times-weekly abdominal pain	3 (75.0%)	22 (95.7%)	14 (70.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.001
Moderate/severe stress	2 (50.0%)	10 (43.5%)	10 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.438
Anxiety often/almost always	3 (75.0%)	9 (39.1%)	8 (40.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.256
Poor sleep quality	1 (25.0%)	6 (26.1%)	3 (15.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.646
Irregular meal pattern	4 (100.0%)	7 (30.4%)	8 (40.0%)	2 (66.7%)	.056
Functional interference moderate/severe	2 (50.0%)	8 (34.8%)	4 (20.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.349
Work/study affected	4 (100.0%)	11 (47.8%)	10 (50.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.071
Social life affected	4 (100.0%)	7 (30.4%)	8 (40.0%)	0 (0.0%)	.030
Fair/poor quality of life	3 (75.0%)	16 (69.6%)	14 (70.0%)	1 (33.3%)	.613

Note. Values are n (%) unless otherwise indicated. P values are exploratory.

DISCUSSION

The present study shows that IBS in this sample was not limited to bowel symptoms, but was accompanied by substantial psychological, lifestyle, and functional burden. The participants had a mean age of 39.0 ± 10.6 years, and females represented 66.0% of the sample. IBS-D was the most frequent subtype, 46.0%, followed by IBS-M, 40.0%, while IBS-C and IBS-U were less common. This pattern is broadly consistent with recent Bangladeshi student data, where diarrhea-predominant and mixed IBS were also common, although subtype distributions vary across settings and diagnostic contexts [7]. The high proportion of recurrent abdominal pain, 96.0%, pain related to defecation, 98.0%, and at least two Rome IV-associated features, 94.0%, supports the clinical coherence of the enrolled IBS sample. Variation in IBS estimates across studies is expected because prevalence and subtype distribution are influenced by population characteristics, care-seeking patterns, and diagnostic criteria [1, 4, 5]. Food-related symptom aggravation was reported by 48 participants, 96.0%, making dietary sensitivity one of the most prominent clinical findings. Irregular meal pattern was present in 42.0%, and it was significantly associated with moderate/severe stress, 61.9% vs 31.0%, OR 3.61, 95% CI 1.11-11.76, p = 0.044. Mahyoub et al. similarly reported dietary habits as relevant factors in IBS among medical students, particularly carbonated drinks and coffee intake [12]. The present finding does not establish whether irregular meals increase stress, stress disrupts eating patterns, or both occur together, but it supports the clinical importance of dietary and lifestyle assessment in IBS care. Psychological burden was also notable. Moderate or severe stress was present in 44.0%, anxiety often or almost always in 40.0%, and symptom

worsening during stress in 90.0%. These findings closely support the “beyond the gut” framing of the study. Hasan et al. reported that IBS among private university students in Dhaka was associated with mental health status, with higher likelihood among females and participants with stress or anxiety symptoms [8]. Mohammed et al. also found significant association between IBS and anxiety-depressive disorders, while Abdelaziz et al. reported that increasing anxiety was associated with increased IBS symptoms among females [9, 10]. The present study extends this pattern in a clinical Bangladeshi sample by showing that stress was not only common, but also linked with functional outcomes. Functional impairment was frequent. Work or study was affected in 50.0%, social life in 38.0%, and overall quality of life was fair or poor in 68.0%. Moderate/severe stress was significantly associated with work or study impairment, 68.2% vs 35.7%, OR 3.86, 95% CI 1.18-12.61, p = 0.045, and social life impairment, 54.5% vs 25.0%, OR 3.60, 95% CI 1.09-11.93, p = 0.043. These findings are consistent with Grover et al., who described IBS as associated with mood, anxiety, sleep comorbidity, and role impairment, and with Faresjö et al., who demonstrated that gastrointestinal symptoms in IBS affect daily work [13, 14]. El-Salhy et al. also reported substantial quality-of-life and social-function impairment among IBS patients, although their burden estimates were higher than the present study, possibly reflecting differences in sample size, survey method, and patient selection [15]. Subtype-based findings should be interpreted cautiously because IBS-C and IBS-U groups were small. Female sex was highest in IBS-D, 87.0%, and daily or several-times-weekly abdominal pain was also highest in IBS-D, 95.7%. Social life impairment varied across subtypes, but sparse cells limit the stability of these comparisons.

Similarly, treatment-related findings should be interpreted descriptively only. Although 92.0% sought medical treatment and 98.0% reported improvement, the cross-sectional design cannot determine treatment effectiveness. Overall, the study supports a clinical profile of IBS in which gastrointestinal symptoms coexist with psychological distress, dietary aggravation, work or study impairment, social disruption, and reduced quality of life. The findings align with the gut-brain interaction model of IBS and indicate that clinical assessment in Bangladeshi IBS patients should routinely include stress, anxiety, sleep, meal pattern, and functional impact. Because the sample size was small and the design was observational and cross-sectional, the associations should be viewed as exploratory rather than causal.

LIMITATIONS

This was a single-centre observational study with a small sample size of 50 participants, so the findings may not be generalizable to all IBS patients in Bangladesh. Because of the cross-sectional design, associations between stress, lifestyle factors, and functional impairment cannot be interpreted as causal. Some variables were self-reported, which may introduce recall or response bias.

CONCLUSION

This study showed that IBS was associated with a considerable clinical, psychological, and functional burden among the study participants. IBS-D was the most frequent subtype, reported in 46.0%, followed by IBS-M in 40.0%. Food-related symptom aggravation was reported by 96.0%, while stress-related worsening of IBS symptoms was reported by 90.0%. Psychological burden was also common, with 44.0% having moderate or severe stress and 40.0% reporting anxiety often or almost

always. Functional impairment was evident, as work or study performance was affected in 50.0%, social life in 38.0%, and fair or poor quality of life was reported by 68.0%. These findings support the need to assess IBS beyond gastrointestinal symptoms, with attention to psychological stress, anxiety, dietary triggers, lifestyle pattern, and quality of life.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

None declared

ETHICAL APPROVAL

The study was approved by the Institutional Ethics Committee

RECOMMENDATION

Patients with IBS should be assessed using an integrated clinical approach that includes gastrointestinal symptoms, psychological stress, anxiety symptoms, meal pattern, sleep quality, and functional impairment. Dietary counselling, stress management, lifestyle modification, and psychological screening should be considered as part of routine IBS care. Larger multicentre studies with validated psychological and quality-of-life scales are recommended to confirm these findings and better define the clinical and psychosocial burden of IBS in Bangladesh.

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